

Thermal cycling damage of silica refractories for high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES) – Can it be healed?

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ABSTRACT

Silica refractories are promising materials for high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES), because they exhibit excellent thermal cycling properties, unless cooled below a critical temperature (usually assumed to be 600 °C). When cooling down to room temperature severe damage can occur, which can be conveniently monitored via the impulse excitation technique (IET). This damage is most severe when the cycling maximum temperature is low. The question is whether this damage can be healed again. In this short contribution we show that severe damage in silica refractories, caused by heating from room temperature to 300 °C and back again to room temperature, can indeed be healed by thermal cycling to 1300 °C. The healed material is actually better than the pristine material.

1. Introduction

Silica refractories have a long history, going back to the 19th century [1–5]. Although the use of silica refractories has been decreasing during the last five decades, both due to the decline of their use in the iron and steel industry and due to the long lifetime of high-quality silica refractories, there is currently a revival of research activities in this field [6–10], in particular in China [11–15], and there are of course several niche applications in which silica refractories are essential or even irreplaceable, e.g. coke oven linings, glass melter roofs and recuperators (so-called Cowper stoves or Cowpers), where they can be used for the dome and the upper checkerwork [16–20]. The latter application is closely related to a new perspective field of application, viz. as thermo-accumulative materials for high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES). The basic idea is to use the electrical energy from solar collector systems to heat up the refractories and to extract this stored energy later when needed e.g. in the form of heat. Both the adequate specific heat [17,21,22] and the relatively high thermal conductivity [13,23] make silica refractories a material of choice for this application. However, the sensitivity to thermal cycling below 600 °C may be considered as a problem. In this paper we indicate a way how this problem can be solved, so that HT-TES systems based on silica refractories can finally be used as “rechargeable batteries” for HT-TES even if the temperature falls occasionally below 600 °C or even to room temperature.

Silica refractories have unique properties that cannot be achieved by any other material. The most important of these, apart from the high creep resistance [24] and refractoriness, is the extremely low (and at high temperatures above approximately 800 °C slightly negative) coefficient of thermal expansion, which makes silica refractories very resistant against thermal shock and very useful for thermal cycling at high temperatures (above 600 °C [16–18]). Moreover, while the specific heat of silica refractories and its temperature dependence [16,21,22] is comparable to other refractories [17], silica refractories have a relatively high thermal conductivity [13,23], higher e.g. than fireclay refractories of comparable porosity [17]. All these properties of silica refractories are based on the unique properties of the silica polymorphs cristobalite and tridymite. However, for the same reason, silica refractories are extremely sensitive to thermal cycling in the temperature range from room temperature to 300 °C, because this is the temperature range in which reversible phase transitions occur between the low- and high-temperature subpolymorphs of cristobalite and tridymite. These phase transitions are connected with volume changes that amount to 0.6 % in the case of tridymite and up to 5.6 % in the case of cristobalite [25], lead to significant changes in the mechanical properties and can cause severe damage by microcracking. Now the impulse excitation technique (IET) [26,27] has turned out to be the most useful tool for monitoring these changes, both the reversible phase transitions with their well-known hysteresis [28–31] and the irreversible changes resulting from damage accumulation by microcracking [7,15,29]. The elastic

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moduli measured by IET are mechanical key properties and to a certain degree their temperature dependence can be expected to reflect also the temperature dependence of other mechanical properties, e.g. strength.

Earlier work focusing on the temperature dependence of Young's modulus, as determined via the impulse excitation technique (IET), has shown that damage accumulation due to thermal cycling from room temperature (RT) and back occurs when the cycle maximum temperature (CMT) is 800 or 1000 °C [29], but not when it is 1200 °C [28,30]. Moreover, recent IET studies of thermal cycling of silica refractories have confirmed that heating to 900 and 1100 °C leads to damage accumulation, while heating to 1300 and 1500 °C leads to healing of the material, i.e. the RT value of Young's modulus after cooling is even higher than before heating [32]. In other words, thermal cycling from RT to temperatures below 1200 °C leads to damage accumulation, whereas thermal cycling to higher temperatures is expected to have a healing effect. However, it has not been ascertained so far whether thermal cycling to temperatures higher than 1200 °C can really heal silica refractories that have been severely damaged by low-temperature cycling. This will be demonstrated in the present paper.

2. Material and method

The materials investigated in this work are prototype silica refractories produced by P-D Refractories CZ a. s. (since 2023 RHI Magnesita Czech Republic a. s.), originally fired with a maximum temperature of 1430 °C, containing 94.2 % SiO₂ and 4.3 % CaO, the remaining components being Fe₂O₃ (0.6 %), Al₂O₃ (0.5 %), and only traces of other impurities, as determined via X-ray fluorescence (XRF) analysis on a PERFORM'X Sequential X-ray Fluorescence Spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The phase composition, as determined via X-ray diffraction (XRD) on an Empyrean Series 3 Diffractometer (Malvern PANalytical, The Netherlands), revealed 44.7 % cristobalite, 47.5 % tridymite, 6.0 % pseudowollastonite and 1.8 % X-ray amorphous phase (glass phase), the latter (determined with ZnO as an internal standard) probably forming thin layers along the grain boundaries. The apparent density, determined via mercury porosimetry on an Autopore IV 9500 Porosimeter (Micromeritics, USA), is 2.33 g/cm³, the open porosity, determined via the Archimedes method in water, is 21 %. Further details on the composition, microstructure and properties of these materials can be found in a recent paper [32], but are less relevant in the present context.

The IET measurements in the present work have been made according to the corresponding ASTM standards [26,27], using a Resonant Frequency and Damping Analyzer (RFDA 23, IMCE, Belgium) with a special setup and alumina sample support integrated in a high-temperature furnace (HT 1600, IMCE, Belgium), see Fig. 1.

Using this IET equipment and setup, Young's modulus is extracted from the fundamental mode of flexural vibrations using the equation [26,27].

$$E = 0.9465 \cdot (mf^2) \cdot \left(\frac{L^3}{bh^3}\right) \cdot \Psi\left(\nu, \frac{h}{L}\right) \quad (1)$$

where f is the resonant frequency, m , L , b , and h are sample mass, length, width, and height, respectively, and Ψ is a sample shape correction factor that depends on the Poisson ratio ν and the aspect ratio of the sample (for our sample very close to unity). The temperature dependences of Young's modulus and damping have been determined using preset heating and cooling rates of 5 °C/min. Cycle maximum temperatures (CMTs) were 300 °C, 1300 °C, 300 °C and 1300 °C for the first, second, third and fourth thermal cycle, respectively. The CMT of 300 °C was chosen for damaging the sample because above that temperature both tridymite and cristobalite have already undergone the transitions to their high-temperature phases, and thus thermal cycling with such a low CMT can be assumed to be most critical, i.e. damage most severe. We are not aware of any other work that investigates the

Fig. 1. Silica refractory sample on alumina sample support for flexural vibrations.

thermal cycling behavior of silica refractories at such a low CMT. On the other hand, the CMT of 1300 °C has been chosen because, on the basis of recent work [32], it can be expected to be sufficiently high for healing the damaged sample.

Thermal cycling damage can be quantified via the damage parameter defined as

$$D_E = 1 - \frac{E_{final}}{E_{initial}} \quad (2)$$

where $E_{initial}$ is Young's modulus before heating and E_{final} is Young's modulus after cooling. In the absence of damage this parameter is 0, for a completely fractured, disintegrated sample this parameter is 1. Similarly, the degree of healing can be quantified by the healing parameter

$$H_E = \frac{E_{final}}{E_{initial}} \quad (3)$$

which is larger than 1 in the case of healing, smaller than 1 in the case of damage and 1 in the absence of both healing and damage. Alternatively, one may obviously use the definition of the damage parameter, Equation (2), and interpret negative values of this parameter as healing and *vice versa*.

Apart from elastic properties, such as Young's modulus, also anelastic features of behavior can be monitored using the IET as a function of temperature, in particular damping, which can be quantified via the so-called inverse quality factor [31].

$$Q^{-1} = \frac{k}{\pi f} \quad (4)$$

where k is the amplitude decay constant of an exponential fit to the hull curve of the nonlinear amplitude decrease of the flexural vibration [31].

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 2 shows the overall results up to 1300 °C, and Fig. 3 shows a detailed view of the data up to 400 °C (the cooling data have been corrected for the very small irreversible linear expansion of the sample after cycling (0.3 %)). The results show the typical hysteresis effects that are well known for silica refractories [7,15,28–30], including the hysteresis (thermal history dependence) of Young's modulus (vertical direction) and the hysteresis in the phase transition temperatures of tridymite and cristobalite (horizontal direction). Since this behavior is well known for silica refractories and has been discussed abundantly in previous papers [28–30], it will not be commented here.

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of Young's modulus during thermal cycling (heating/up and cooling/down) from and to room temperature (RT) with cycle maximum temperatures of 300 °C (first cycle/I), 1300 °C (second cycle/II), 300 °C (third cycle/III), and 1300 °C (fourth cycle/IV).

Fig. 3. Detailed view of the low-temperature range of Fig. 2.

The most important point of these results is the following: After thermal cycling to 300 °C Young's modulus has decreased from 11 GPa to 7 GPa, resulting in a damage parameter of $0.36 = 36\%$. This damage is obviously caused by microcracking due to the volumetric changes occurring during the repeated phase transitions between the low- and high-temperature subpolymorphs of cristobalite and tridymite in the course of thermal cycling. Previous work has shown that repeated cycling would indeed lead to damage accumulation [7,15,29] and possibly to the complete destruction of the sample after a sufficient number of cycles. However, thermal cycling with a CMT of 1300 °C is able to completely heal the damage caused by the previous cycling to 300 °C (healing parameter $1.09 = 109\%$) and – more than that – after cycling to 1300 °C the sample exhibits even higher Young's modulus than before cycling (12 GPa instead of 11 GPa, see Figs. 2 and 3). Moreover, subsequent cycling to 300 °C (third cycle) leads to less severe damage than cycling of the pristine (previously uncycled) material

(from 12 GPa to slightly below 10 GPa), resulting in a damage parameter of only $0.17 = 17\%$, and another cycle to 1300 °C (fourth cycle) does not show any further changes (neither improvement nor deterioration) of the material. It is thus clear that thermal cycling to sufficiently high temperatures is able to heal silica refractories that have been damaged by previous low-temperature cycling. Fig. 4 shows the healing parameter as a function of the cycle number. In particular, there is no reason to assume that silica refractories could principally not survive cycling down to room temperature, although of course damage accumulation by repeated low-temperature cycling should generally be avoided wherever possible, and damaged samples should be allowed to regenerate by letting them undergo a high-temperature cycle (e.g. with a CMT of 1300 °C, as shown in this paper).

An interesting by-result of this work is the following: when the temperature dependences of Young's modulus during heating and cooling are normalized with respect to the corresponding room

Fig. 4. Healing parameter as a function of the cycle number (the horizontal reference line represents the pristine state of the material before thermal cycling).

temperature values (before heating and after cooling, respectively, as shown in Figs. 5 and 6), the phase transition temperatures from low-to high-cristobalite during heating are the same in all four thermal cycles (with the highest rate at approximately 240 °C), whereas the phase transition temperatures from high-to low-cristobalite during cooling are significantly different for the two types of cycles with different CMTs, viz. 220 °C after heating to 300 °C and 200 °C after heating to 1300 °C. To the best of our knowledge this is the first observation of this kind. It has to be emphasized that the interesting point here is not the hysteresis of the transition temperature (which is well known for cristobalite) but the fact that the hysteresis is reproducibly different for different CMTs. The reproducibility of this phenomenon indicates that it cannot be a consequence of irreversible changes in the phase composition and microstructure. Therefore we conjecture that the healing of the microcracks (mainly circumferential cracks around the cristobalite grains) after heating to 1300 °C (due to the melting of the glass phase) constrains the cristobalite grains (forming a coherent interface with the glassy matrix), thus shifting the volume-changing transition from high-cristobalite (density 2.20 g/cm³) to low-cristobalite (density 2.32 g/cm³) to lower temperatures, where the interfacial stresses become

sufficiently high. In the unhealed material (i.e. after cycling to 300 °C) this constraint is absent, so that the transition during cooling can occur already at a significantly higher temperature. During subsequent reheating of the material after cycling to 1300 °C the reverse transition occurs in an already cracked material. The temperature of this transition is therefore very similar to that after cycling to 300 °C. The fact that the transition temperatures during heating are so similar is actually somewhat surprising, because (as shown above) the degree of microcracking is certainly much higher after cycling to 300 °C than after cycling to 1300 °C. This might be caused by the fact that after cycling to 300 °C not only circumferential cracks around the cristobalite grains are formed but other cracks as well, e.g. in the tridymite-based matrix phase. In this context a minor detail should not escape the attention of the reader, viz. the fact that there seems to be an evolution in the temperature range of the tridymite transitions during heating, see Fig. 5, whereas such an evolution is absent during cooling, see Fig. 6.

Last but not least, Fig. 7 shows the temperature dependence of damping, as quantified via the so-called inverse quality factor defined in Equation (4) [31]. Interestingly, below 300 °C there are no significant differences in damping before and after cycling to any temperature (CMT 300 °C or 1300 °C). Despite the typically large scatter of experimental values, damping exhibits a clearly decreasing trend from values of 0.02 ± 0.01 at room temperature to below 0.01 at 400 °C, followed by a steep increase above 700 °C to values of higher than 0.03. This behavior indicates that maximum microcrack closure is attained during heating above 500 °C and microcrack re-opening occurs during cooling below 500 °C. The steep damping increase during heating above 700 °C is presumably caused by softening of the glass phase at the grain boundaries, and the reverse effect appears upon cooling.

4. Summary and conclusions

In summary, it has been shown in this work that while thermal cycling from room temperature to 300 °C causes severe damage in silica refractories, thermal cycling to 1300 °C is able to heal those microcracks that are primarily responsible for the damage-induced reduction of Young's modulus. After healing the materials can even exhibit better mechanical properties than before damaging and be less prone to damage in subsequent thermal cycles. Moreover, after heating to 1300 °C the cristobalite transition during cooling occurs at a temperature that is 20 K lower than after heating to 300 °C, i.e. lower

Fig. 5. Temperature dependence of the normalized Young modulus during heating in the four thermal cycles; note that the phase transition from low-to high-cristobalite occurs at approximately the same temperature (with highest rate at around 240 °C).

Fig. 6. Temperature dependence of the normalized Young modulus during cooling in the four thermal cycles; transition from high-to low-cristobalite at significantly different temperatures (220 °C after heating to 300 °C and 200 °C after heating to 1300 °C); note that in contrast to the heating curves there is no evolution in the temperature range of the tridymite transitions during cooling.

Fig. 7. Temperature dependence of damping (inverse quality factor) in the four thermal cycles.

temperatures (or higher thermal expansion mismatch stresses) are required to cause cracking of the healed materials. Damping shows a minimum in the temperature range 500–700 °C and steep increases below and above this range, which is caused by microcracking (during cooling) and softening of the glass phase (during heating), respectively. The healing mechanism demonstrated in this work may be important for using silica refractories in high-temperature thermal energy storage (HT-TES) applications.

Data availability statement

The original raw data for this paper are available at <https://zenodo.org/records/11473836> (DOI number: 10.5281/zenodo.11473836).

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Eva Gregorová: Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation. **Lucie Kotrbová:** Investigation, Data curation. **Willi Pabst:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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